

1 **The bacterial community inhabiting temperate deciduous forests is vertically stratified and**
2 **undergoes seasonal dynamics**

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11

12 **Abstract**

13

14 Bacterial communities living in forest soils contribute to the decomposition of organic matter and
15 the recycling of nutrients in these ecosystems and form one of the most diverse habitats on Earth.

16 Unfortunately, due to difficulty in culturing soil bacteria, the understanding of their ecology is still
17 limited. In the case of temperate deciduous forests, soil microbial communities face large seasonal

18 variations in environmental conditions, such as temperature or moisture. Moreover, the supply of
19 nutrients also differs due to seasonal processes, such as the allocation of photosynthates into soil

20 by the roots of primary producers or the seasonal input of fresh litter. The aim of this study was to
21 reveal how the bacterial community responds to these seasonal processes in the litter and soil of a

22 *Quercus petraea* forest. Bacterial communities from litter and from the organic and mineral
23 horizons of soil were analyzed during the four seasons of the year by 16S rRNA gene

24 pyrosequencing. The results revealed that the composition of the bacterial community is horizon
25 specific. The litter horizon had a higher relative abundance of *Proteobacteria* and *Bacteroidetes*
26 than soil, while the organic and mineral horizons had a higher abundance of *Acidobacteria*,
27 *Firmicutes* and *Actinobacteria* than litter. Moreover, the bacterial community was significantly
28 affected by seasonality in all horizons. Bacterial communities in the litter showed significant
29 differences between the vegetation season (May and July) and the autumn and winter seasons
30 (October, February). In mineral soil, bacterial community composition was specific in the summer,
31 when it was significantly different from all other seasons, with a larger number of taxa described
32 as rhizosphere and mycorrhizosphere inhabitants. The results indicate that litter decomposition is
33 the main driver of bacterial community composition in this horizon. In contrast to reports on fungal
34 communities, bacterial community composition in mineral soil responds to the seasonal peaks of
35 rhizodeposition in the summer.

36

37 **Keywords:** *bacterial community, deciduous forest, forest soil, litter, decomposition, seasonality*

38

39 **1. Introduction**

40

41 Temperate deciduous forests represent one of the most important carbon (C) sinks in
42 Europe, Asia and Northern America and contribute to the health of the planet (Janssens et al.,
43 2003). The flux of C into these ecosystems is mainly mediated by the photosynthetic fixation of
44 CO₂ by broadleaved trees, its allocation belowground via tree roots in the form of root exudates
45 and root litter and the accumulation of the aboveground litter on the forest floor due to yearly
46 seasonal litterfall. This pool of C-rich organic matter (OM) is used as a carbon and energy source

47 by a diverse community of microorganisms, responsible for its transformation and mineralization
48 throughout the year (Uroz et al., 2011, Rasche et al., 2011 and Voříšková et al., 2014). Microbial
49 communities thus play a critical role in soil biogeochemical processes, as the main drivers of C
50 efflux from the ecosystem and its transformation, resulting in the formation of a forest soil profile,
51 one of the most diverse habitats on Earth (Roesch et al., 2007). The yearly input of litter and the
52 ongoing decomposition process in forests result in three distinct topsoil compartments: the litter,
53 the organic (or humic) horizon and the mineral soil horizon. This vertical stratification is
54 characterized by a decrease in the content and quality of OM with soil depth, which is accompanied
55 by changes in the activity of extracellular enzymes and in the size and composition of the microbial
56 community (Sinsabaugh et al., 2002 and Šnajdr et al., 2008a).

57 In addition to the organic matter in the soil, microbial activity is also influenced by environmental
58 factors, with the variations in temperature and moisture across different seasons being the most
59 notable (Brockett et al., 2012). In a temperate forest, temperature variation due to seasonality
60 directly influences C fluxes in the ecosystem (Baldrian et al., 2013). Most importantly, the
61 photosynthetic production of plants is limited to the vegetation period. As a consequence, the
62 increasing rate of photosynthesis during the spring and summer is associated with the deposition
63 of easily decomposable compounds, such as amino acids, sugars and organic acids, into plant roots
64 and the deeper soil horizons either directly or in a process mediated by root-associated mycorrhizal
65 fungi (Ekblad and Högberg, 2001). The annual period of litterfall restricted to autumn and early
66 winter leads to the seasonal accumulation of large amounts of nutrients on the soil surface. The
67 continuous decomposition of litter results in gradual changes in its quality until the next litterfall
68 (Šnajdr et al., 2011 and Baldrian et al., 2013). Microbial communities are subject to these profound
69 changes in nutrient content and composition during the year, which results in seasonal changes in

70 their abundance and activity (Kaiser et al., 2010, Kaiser et al., 2011 and Voříšková et al., 2014).
71 Importantly, the understanding of the seasonal dynamics of microbial communities is necessary
72 for the prediction of the future response of temperate deciduous forests to global climate change
73 and its effects on the C balance in the ecosystem (Schindlbacher et al., 2012 and Rousk et al.,
74 2012).

75 Several previous studies reported that seasonality may affect the structure of microbial
76 communities and the functional properties of soil microorganisms in the temperate forest,
77 suggesting that microbial dynamics is mainly influenced by changing temperature, moisture and
78 nutrient availability (Collignon et al., 2011, Chemidlin Prevost-Boure et al., 2011, Rasche et al.,
79 2011 and Koranda et al., 2013). However, the resolution of most of this work was limited by the
80 use of methods based on DNA fingerprinting or qPCR, which are insufficient for the
81 characterization of the community composition (Osborn et al., 2000 and Zhang et al., 2008). High-
82 throughput DNA pyrosequencing provides more detailed information on microbial communities
83 inhabiting soils (Roesch et al., 2007) and has been successfully used to explore the ecology and
84 diversity of soil microorganisms in a wide variety of types of ecosystems (Lauber et al., 2009,
85 Eilers et al., 2012, Uroz et al., 2013 and Williams et al., 2013). Recently, Voříšková et al. (2014)
86 applied pyrosequencing for the in-depth description of the seasonal development of the structure
87 and functioning of fungal communities and demonstrated that the fungal abundance and
88 community composition undergoes seasonal changes. The effects of seasonality on bacterial
89 communities using pyrosequencing was highlighted by Kuffner et al. (2012), who found no
90 substantial differences in a mountainous forest between these communities across the seasons.
91 Unfortunately, that study only compared summer and was performed in a forest with prevailing
92 evergreen coniferous trees where the litter input is not seasonally restricted. Moreover, the

93 limitation of the study to soil makes any inferences on carbon balance difficult because the bulk
94 of the organic matter loss and microbial activity occurs in litter (Šnajdr et al., 2011 and Šnajdr et
95 al., 2008a). The analysis of a deciduous forest ecosystem considering both litter and soil are
96 unavailable.

97 The aim of this work was to fill this knowledge gap by describing the bacterial community living
98 in the litter and upper soil and determining how it changes throughout the year. We hypothesized
99 that phenomena such as litter input, temperature and moisture variation and the seasonal pattern
100 of C rhizodeposition would affect the bacterial community composition across the year. The data
101 describing the bacterial community composition were obtained from the same study that analyzed
102 the seasonality of fungi (Voříšková et al., 2014). That study showed that the fungal community is
103 stratified in the soil profile and its composition in litter undergoes profound seasonal changes as a
104 consequence of changing litter chemistry. In contrast, despite the fact that root-associated fungi
105 dominated deeper soil horizons where they could have theoretically responded to changes in root
106 exudation, the seasonal changes in fungal community composition were minor. Based on that
107 observation, we suggest that the seasonality of bacterial communities is horizon specific and most
108 pronounced in the litter because there are many bacterial taxa that are involved in decomposition
109 in forest ecosystems (Štursová et al., 2012). The parallel exploration of the fungal and bacterial
110 community dynamics should also complete the picture of microbial response to ecosystem
111 seasonality and reveal possible differences among these ecophysiologicaly distinct groups of
112 microorganisms (Boer et al., 2005).

113

114 **2. Materials and Methods**

115

116 *2.1. Site description and sample collection*

117

118 The experimental study site was situated in a sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*) forest in the
119 Xaverovský Háj Natural Reserve in the Czech Republic (50°5'38"N, 14°36'48"E). Soil and litter
120 chemistry and decomposition processes have been studied in the area previously (Šnajdr et al.,
121 2008a, Šnajdr et al., 2011 and Baldrian et al., 2013), as well as the structure and functioning of
122 fungal communities associated with litter and soil (Voříšková and Baldrian, 2013 and Voříšková
123 et al., 2014). The soil was an acidic cambisol with developed litter (L), organic (humic, H), and
124 mineral (Ah and A) horizons. Vegetation season defined as the presence of living leaves on trees
125 starts in mid-April and lasts until the end of September. This study used the material collected for
126 the study of (Voříšková et al., 2014). Sampling of the topsoil was performed in the spring (9 May,
127 approximately two weeks after the emergence of leaves), summer (29 July), autumn (28 October,
128 during the late phase of litterfall) and winter (19 February). Soil samples were collected in four
129 defined plots (10 m², approximately 100 m from each other) at the sampling site. Six soil cores
130 were collected at each sampling plot using sampling tubes with a 4.5-cm diameter and were divided
131 into litter (L horizon, ~ 0.5-1 cm), H horizon (~ 1-3 cm) and Ah horizon (upper portion, up to a
132 depth of 5 cm). Samples of the L horizon were cut into approx. 0.25 cm² pieces, while the soil
133 samples were sieved using a 2-mm sieve. The resulting material was combined to yield a composite
134 sample from each horizon and plot. Subsamples for chemical analyses, quantification of microbial
135 biomass and DNA extraction were frozen and stored at -45°C, and subsamples for enzyme analysis
136 were stored at 4°C. In each sample, soil moisture content, pH, C and N content and the activity of
137 selected extracellular enzymes was determined following the methods of (Voříšková et al., 2014).

138

139 *2.2. DNA extraction and 454-pyrosequencing of 16S rRNA*

140

141 Total DNA was isolated from 0.3 g of soil or litter material using the modified Miller-SK method
142 (Sagova-Mareckova et al., 2008). Bacterial 16S rRNA genes were PCR-amplified with the primer
143 pair eub530f and eub1110br modified from Dowd et al. (2008) and Baldrian et al. (2012).
144 Amplification was performed in two steps as described previously (Baldrian et al., 2012). In the
145 first step, each of three independent 50 µl reactions per DNA sample contained 1 U of OmniTaq
146 PCR buffer, 0.4 µM of each primer, 0.2 µM dNTPs mix, and 1.5 U of polymerase (Pfu DNA
147 polymerase: OmniTaq DNA polymerase, 1:24). The amplification was carried out using the
148 following program: initial denaturation at 94°C for 5 min, 35 cycles of at 94°C for 1 min, 62°C for
149 1 min and 70°C for 1 min, with a final extension step at 72°C for 10 min. PCR products from
150 triplicates were pooled and purified using the MinElute PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen, Hilden,
151 Germany). Products were used as the template for a second PCR using composite primers
152 containing multiplex identifiers. The second PCR was carried out in a total volume of 50 µL,
153 containing 1 U of DyNAzyme DNA polymerase, 1.5 µl dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), 0.2 µM
154 dNTPs mix, 0.08 µM of forward fusion primer (eub530f, tag sequence, 454-specific sequence),
155 0.08 µM of reverse fusion primer (eub1100br, 454-specific sequence), 3 U of polymerase (Pfu
156 DNA polymerase: DyNAzyme polymerase, 1:24) and 100 ng of template DNA. The PCR program
157 was as follows: 94°C for 5 min; 10 cycles of 94°C for 1 min, and 72°C for 1 min; followed by
158 70°C for 10 min. PCR products were purified using Agencourt AMPure XP (Beckman Coulter,
159 Beverly, MA, USA), and the concentration was measured using a Qubit 2.0 Fluorometer (Life
160 Technologies, Carlsbad, CA, USA). Subsequently, an equimolar mix of PCR products from all
161 samples was prepared and purified again through electrophoresis in a gel, using the Wizard SV

162 Gel and PCR Clean-Up System (Promega, Madison, WI, USA). The resulting sample was purified
163 using the Agencourt AMPure XP and MiniElute PCR Purification Kit and sequenced on a GS
164 Junior 454-pyrosequencer (Roche, Basel, Switzerland).

165

166 *2.3. Processing of pyrosequencing data*

167

168 The pyrosequencing data were processed using the pipeline SEED using the proposed procedures
169 of standardized data analysis (Větrovský and Baldrian, 2013). Pyrosequencing noise reduction was
170 performed using Denoiser 0.851 (Reeder and Knight, 2010), and chimeric sequences were detected
171 using UCHIME (Edgar et al., 2011) and deleted. The sequences were shortened to 380 bases and
172 clustered using Usearch (Edgar, 2010) at a 98% similarity level. Consensus sequences were
173 constructed for each cluster, and the OTUs were constructed by clustering these consensus
174 sequences at 97% identity (Lundberg et al., 2012). The abundance data reported in this paper are
175 based on this dataset of sequence abundances and should be taken as proxies of taxon abundances
176 only with caution. The closest hits were assigned using the Ribosomal Database Project (RDP)
177 (Cole et al., 2014). Sequence data have been deposited in the MG-RAST public database
178 (<http://metagenomics.anl.gov/>, data set number 4626536.3) (Meyer et al., 2008).

179

180 *2.4. Diversity and statistical analysis*

181

182 The pipeline SEED was used for calculations of species richness, diversity (expressed as the
183 Shannon-Wiener index), and Evenness using 1,400 sequences randomly selected from each
184 sample. Due to technical and statistical reproducibility of OTU abundance for low abundance

185 OTUs (Lundberg et al., 2012), only those OTUs with an abundance $\geq 0.5\%$ in ≥ 5 samples
186 (abundant OTU) were used for testing for the differences in abundance. Phylogenetic differences
187 between communities were visualized using a principle coordinates analysis (PCoA) of the
188 pairwise weighted UniFrac distances (Lozupone and Knight, 2005), and a heat map for the
189 hierarchical clustering of OTU abundances in samples was generated with the R package
190 (<http://www.R-project.org/>). Data on taxon abundances were square root transformed before
191 statistical analysis. The significance of observed differences among bacterial communities among
192 horizons or seasons was determined by PERMANOVA with Bray-Curtis similarity after 9999
193 permutations. Differences in the abundance of individual bacterial taxa were analyzed using one-
194 way analysis of variance with Fisher's least significant difference *post hoc* test. Differences with
195 a $P < 0.05$ were regarded as statistically significant. Principal component analysis (PCA) was used
196 to visualize the relationships between plot-normalized OTU abundances and environmental
197 variables. Statistical analyses were conducted in Past 3.02a (Hammer et al., 2001) and in Statistica
198 7 (Statsoft, Tulsa, OK, USA).

199

200 **3. Results**

201

202 3.1. Soil characteristics

203

204 The data obtained in a previous study (Voříšková et al., 2014) revealed that the physicochemical
205 properties of forest soil change significantly with the soil depth. In particular, the content of
206 organic matter, N content, pH and activity of extracellular enzymes all decreased with depth, while

207 the soil moisture content increased. Seasonality also affected soil properties during the year,
208 resulting in significant differences of soil chemistry and enzyme activity among seasons (Fig. S1).
209 In total, 144,617 raw sequences were obtained using 454-pyrosequencing, of which 124,391
210 remained for analysis after quality filtering, denoising and the removal of short and chimeric
211 sequences. An average of 2,590 sequences was obtained per sample (minimum 1,400). Sequences
212 were clustered into 9,942 OTUs, including 6,615 singletons.

213

214 3.2. Alpha diversity patterns

215

216 The species richness was significantly higher in the L horizon than in the H and Ah horizons
217 (paired Wilcoxon test, $P < 0.01$), while the difference between the H and Ah horizons was not
218 significant (Fig. S2). Moreover, L horizon showed significant seasonal differences among seasons,
219 with the peak in the spring (ANOVA, $F = 6.375$, $P = 0.007$); in Ah, a significant difference was
220 only recorded between spring and summer. When expressed as the Shannon-Wiener index,
221 diversity decreased with depth, with the L horizon being significantly more diverse than the H
222 horizon and the Ah horizon (paired Wilcoxon test, $P = 0.015$ and $P = 0.0004$, respectively). In L,
223 summer and spring samples showed significantly higher diversity than those from autumn and
224 winter (ANOVA, $F = 12.85$, $P = 0.0004$). Also in H and Ah, spring samples were more diverse
225 than autumn samples. The Evenness of the community was significantly lower in the Ah horizon
226 than in the H and L (paired Wilcoxon test, $P < 0.01$) horizons, while in the L and Ah horizons, the
227 Evenness tended to be higher in summer than in winter.

228

229 3.3. Bacterial taxonomic composition in the horizons

230

231 The bacterial community was dominated by sequences assigned to *Acidobacteria* (38%),
232 *Proteobacteria* (32%), *Actinobacteria* (12%) and *Bacteroidetes* (9%) (Fig. 1). The most abundant
233 subgroups in *Acidobacteria* were Gp1 (27%), Gp2 (6%) and Gp3 (5%). In the case of
234 *Proteobacteria*, the dominant classes were *Alphaproteobacteria* (17%) and *Gammaproteobacteria*
235 (9%), followed by *Betaproteobacteria* (3%) and *Deltaproteobacteria* (3%). Other less abundant
236 phyla were the *Verrucomicrobia* (3%) and *Firmicutes* (2%).

237 The composition of bacterial communities was significantly affected by both horizon ($P = 0.0001$)
238 and season ($P = 0.0013$) but not by their interaction ($P = 0.1177$; PERMANOVA on Bray-Curtis
239 similarity, 9999 permutations). Soil horizons explained 54% and season explained 9% of total
240 variability. The differences among horizons were apparent on the level of bacterial phyla as well
241 as OTUs (Table S1 and S2). Sequences belonging to *Acidobacteria* increased with the soil depth,
242 except for the sequences of subgroups Gp10, Gp5 and Gp22, which were not found in deeper
243 horizons (Table S1). The abundance of *Actinobacteria*, *Firmicutes*, *Chloroflexi*, and
244 *Planctomycetes* was also highest in the Ah horizon. On the contrary, *Bacteroidetes* and
245 *Proteobacteria* (with the exception of *Deltaproteobacteria*) were most abundant in the L horizon.
246 The composition of bacterial communities was most similar between H and Ah, where 50% of
247 OTUs did not show differences in abundance; 75% and 85% of OTUs exhibited different
248 abundances between L and H and between L and Ah, respectively (Table S2).

249 In total, the best hits to 226 genera were found for the OTUs. The most abundant genera identified
250 in litter included *Bacteroidetes*, such as *Mucilaginibacter*, *Pedobacter*, and *Ferruginibacter*, and
251 *Proteobacteria*, such as *Bradyrhizobium*, *Rhizomicrobium*, *Rhodanobacter*, *Burkholderia*,
252 *Rudaea*, *Luteibacter*, *Sphingobacteria*, *Pseudomonas* and *Novosphingobium* (Table S2). The

253 sequences of the acidobacterial genera *Granulicella* and *Edaphobacter* were found mainly in the
254 L and H horizons, while *Aciditerrimonas* (*Actinobacteria*), *Acidobacterium* (*Acidobacteria*) and
255 *Rhodoplanes* (*Alphaproteobacteria*) were more abundant in mineral soil.

256

257 3.4. Shifts in bacterial community composition with seasons

258

259 Because the composition of bacterial communities among horizons differed profoundly, the
260 seasonal effects on bacterial community composition were analyzed for each horizon separately.

261 The differences in community composition among seasons were significant in all horizons ($P =$
262 0.0005, 0.0088 and 0.0090 for the L, H and Ah, respectively, according to PERMANOVA on

263 Bray-Curtis similarity, 9999 permutations). In L, H, and Ah, 58%, 44% and 40% of selected OTUs,
264 respectively, showed significant differences in relative abundance among seasons (Table S3). In

265 litter, bacterial community composition in the spring and summer was significantly different than

266 in the autumn and winter, while in the Ah horizon, the bacterial community in the summer was

267 significantly different from all other seasons (Fig. S3). This was observed at the level of OTU

268 abundance as well as the phylogenetic distance among communities. In fact, the community

269 composition of the Ah horizon in summer was more similar to the communities in the organic soil

270 (Fig. 2, Fig. 3).

271 Principal component analysis also reflected the differences among bacterial communities among

272 seasons in all horizons (Fig. S3). It also showed that the effects of sites were more pronounced in

273 soil than in litter. In litter (Fig. S3 A), bacterial composition in autumn and winter was positive

274 correlated with the activity of multiple extracellular enzymes (β -glucosidase, β -xylosidase,

275 endocellulase, exocellulase and *N*-acetylglucosaminidase), while the samples from summer were

276 characterized by higher pH and dry mass content. The summer and winter communities were
277 characterized by an increased abundance of Gp1 and Gp2 *Acidobacteria* and the members of the
278 genus *Ferruginibacter*, while *Luteibacter* was highly abundant in the spring (Table S4). In the
279 organic soil (Fig. S3 B), relationships between environmental variables and bacterial community
280 composition were less clear. A higher abundance of Gp2 *Acidobacteria* and *Rhizomicrobium* was
281 observed in the autumn, while *Acidobacterium*, *Collimonas* and *Ferruginibacter* were more
282 abundant in the winter (Table S4). In the mineral soil (Fig. S3 C), the bacterial community in the
283 summer was most different from other seasons, separating along the first axis along with the
284 activity of several extracellular enzymes, N content and pH. The bacterial genera
285 *Mucilaginibacter*, *Rhizomicrobium*, *Burkholderia*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Ferruginibacter*,
286 *Acidobacterium* and *Rhodanobacter* were highly abundant during this season (Table S4).

287

288 **4. Discussion**

289

290 Bacterial communities inhabiting the forest soil are important players in geochemical cycles and
291 the recycling of organic matter, thus playing an essential role in C cycle in these ecosystems
292 (Štursová et al., 2012). Our results showed that forest soil was dominated by the same major groups
293 (*Acidobacteria*, *Proteobacteria*, *Actinobacteria*, and *Bacteroidetes*) reported from acidic soils of
294 various biomes (Lauber et al., 2009 and Peralta et al., 2013). Previous studies of the diversity of
295 bacterial communities pointed out a bias in designed 16S rRNA primers against less abundant
296 groups (Bergmann et al., 2011). Although our study showed a low abundance of phyla, such
297 *Chlamydiae* and *Planctomyces*, we identified abundant sequences belonging to *Verrucomicrobia*
298 in the forest soil. Despite this result, pyrosequencing allows the analysis of a larger number of

300 samples and provides a more robust and accurate analysis of bacterial structure than other methods
301 (Sogin et al., 2006, Liu et al., 2007 and Lauber et al., 2009). The bacterial groups showed a non-
302 uniform distribution along the vertical profile of forest soil. Despite the general dominance of
303 certain taxa, the composition of bacterial communities was highly horizon specific. Similar
304 observations have been reported in studies analyzing horizon effect in bacterial communities in
305 different ecosystems (Will et al., 2010, Eilers et al., 2012 and Baldrian et al., 2012). Contrary to
306 the coniferous forest soil (Eilers et al., 2012), where bacterial diversity did not differ between litter
307 and soil, here we observed a significantly higher bacterial diversity in litter compared to soil.
308 Interestingly, a decrease in diversity with soil depth was also found in the fungal community in a
309 previous study on the same ecosystem (Voříšková et al., 2014). The authors of that study concluded
310 that the higher heterogeneity of nutrient sources in upper horizons was the primary explanation for
311 this observation. Fierer et al. (2007) reported that C availability was the best predictor of phylum-
312 level abundance in soil. In our samples, the litter and organic horizons contained 5 times and 2.5
313 times more organic matter, respectively, than mineral soil. In addition, a soil analysis of this
314 ecosystem demonstrated a large reduction of soil respiration with depth, indicating that the organic
315 matter in the deeper horizon is more recalcitrant (Šnajdr et al., 2008b). This may be the reason for
316 the higher abundance of *Bacteroidetes* and most *Proteobacteria* in the upper horizons, supporting
317 the classification of these phyla as copiotrophic. On the contrary, mineral soil was richer in the
318 oligotrophic *Acidobacteria*. *Acidobacteria* was the most abundant taxa in all samples. While it is
319 known that low pH, as found in this forest soil, is the most prominent factor determining abundance
320 of this bacterial group (Jones et al., 2009 and Lauber et al., 2009), *Acidobacteria* groups such as
321 Gp1, Gp2 and Gp3 dominate soils worldwide (Naether et al., 2012). Although *Acidobacteria*
remains as a poorly studied phylum due to low culturability, these results defend the importance

322 of this phylogenetic group in the structure and function of the forest soil ecosystem (Will et al.,
323 2010 and Uroz et al., 2013).

324 At the genus level, the OTUs also showed vertical stratification. Moreover, most of the genera
325 have been reported as highly abundant in other studies on acidic forest soils (Štursová et al., 2012
326 and Baldrian et al., 2012). Some of these abundant taxa, namely, *Mucilaginibacter*, *Pedobacter*,
327 *Burkholderia* and *Collimonas*, were identified as potentially cellulolytic using Stable Isotope
328 Probing (Štursová et al., 2012). Their contribution to dead plant biomass decomposition is
329 supported by their higher abundance in the upper horizons containing large amounts of cellulosic
330 plant matter (Table S2).

331 Several previous studies focused on the variation of bacterial communities in soil associated with
332 seasonal changes in environmental variables (Lipson, 2007, Chemidlin Prevost-Boure et al., 2011,
333 Collignon et al., 2011, Kuffner et al., 2012 and Williams et al., 2013) and significant differences
334 in bacterial community composition were also observed in this study in all soil horizons. The
335 proposed explanations for observed seasonal differences in bacterial communities vary among
336 studies. Rasche et al. (2011) proposed the variation of soil moisture and temperature as the most
337 likely cause for compositional shifts in bacterial communities in temperate forests. However, a
338 previous exploration of the seasonality of microbial biomass content and activity of multiple
339 extracellular enzymes in the ecosystem of this study showed little seasonal variation in soil
340 moisture (Baldrian et al., 2013). Andretta et al. (2012) connected the observed seasonal changes
341 in the organic and mineral soil to the seasonal fluctuations in nutrient content. This seems to be a
342 plausible explanation for the bacterial community development in the mineral soil in this study,
343 where the summer community was different from other seasons and more similar in composition
344 to samples from the less nutrient-limited organic soil. Warm periods in temperate and boreal

345 forests are characterized by active photosynthesis of trees, with a peak of photosynthate allocation
346 into roots in late summer (Högberg et al., 2010). In addition, mineral soil in summer has the highest
347 N content and the lowest C/N ratio. The possible effect of seasonal root activity on bacterial
348 community composition is supported by the increase in the abundance of those genera which have
349 been described as rhizosphere and mycorrhizosphere inhabitants, such as *Steroidobacter*,
350 *Rhizomicrobium*, *Edaphobacter* or *Burkholderia* (Koch et al., 2008, Ueki et al., 2010, Uroz et al.,
351 2010 and Uroz et al., 2013).

352 In a deciduous forest, the composition and chemistry of the L horizon is highly affected by the
353 input of nutrients from fresh litter each autumn (Baldrian et al., 2013). The microbial community
354 associated with the previous year's litter undergoes successional changes due to variations in the
355 decomposition dynamics of the litter components (Šnajdr et al., 2011 and Voříšková and Baldrian,
356 2013). Because fresh litter supports the highest microbial biomass, these successional changes
357 affect the microbial community in the whole litter horizon, as demonstrated for fungi (Voříšková
358 et al., 2014). Here, we observed that the highest enzyme activity (e.g. of β -glucosidase,
359 endocellulase and endoxylanase) in litter during autumn and winter, shortly after litterfall, is
360 accompanied by a high abundance of bacteria from the genera *Mucilaginibacter*, *Ferruginibacter*,
361 *Pedobacter* and *Collimonas*. These were previously reported to be associated with cellulose
362 decomposition in litter (Štursová et al., 2012). Bacterial OTUs belonging to *Actinobacteria* were
363 more abundant during spring and summer, which is in line with the increase in *Actinobacteria*-
364 specific PLFA markers in litter in the same period of the year ((Šnajdr et al., 2011). These
365 observations indicate that successional development of litter is likely the key process determining
366 the composition of the bacterial community.

367 In agreement with our first hypothesis, our results revealed that bacterial communities inhabiting
368 forest soil are strongly affected by the seasonal changes occurring in these ecosystems. Moreover,
369 the data from this study and a previous study of fungal communities (Voříšková et al., 2014) make
370 it possible to compare the seasonal dynamics of these major groups of microorganisms. Fungal
371 community composition as a whole showed significant seasonal changes only in the litter horizon,
372 characterized by a succession of fungi on litter of various quality, and the emergence of
373 ectomycorrhizal fungi in litter during their summer fruiting (Voříšková et al., 2014). Accordingly,
374 we hypothesized similar dynamics for the bacteria communities. However, our results showed that
375 in contrast to fungi, bacterial communities undergo significant seasonal changes in all soil
376 horizons. While the succession on litter might represent an equally plausible explanation for the
377 bacterial community dynamics in litter, bacteria in mineral soil seem to respond to seasonal peak
378 of rhizodeposition by the increase in rhizosphere and mycorrhizosphere-specific taxa in summer.
379 Although bacterial biomass was not quantified in this study, a previous report from the same
380 ecosystem reported a significantly higher content of bacteria-specific PLFA in mineral soil in the
381 summer (Baldrian et al., 2013), coincident with the increase in fungal biomass (Voříšková et al.,
382 2014). In both cases, the difference in biomass between the summer and winter is approximately
383 twofold and it seems that the seasonal rhizodeposition of photosynthates is the most plausible
384 explanation of this observation.

385

386 **5. Conclusions**

387

388 This study shows that for bacteria, as for fungi, soil communities in a deciduous forest differ in
389 their composition among litter, organic soil and mineral soil. In contrast to fungi, bacterial

390 communities exhibit significant horizon-specific seasonal changes. While the annual changes in
391 litter quality seem to drive the composition of the bacterial community in litter, the specific
392 composition of the summer bacterial community in the mineral soil indicates that the seasonal
393 differences in the activity of tree roots are the major driver. Apparently, plants as primary
394 producers substantially affect microbial community dynamics in a temperate deciduous forest.

395

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563 Figure 1. Bacterial community composition in the litter, organic and mineral soil of a *Quercus*
564 *petraea* forest across seasons. The data represent the means of four replicates per season.
565 Abbreviations: Au – autumn, Wi – winter, Sp – spring, Su – summer.

566

567 Figure 2. Phylogenetic distances among bacterial communities in the litter, organic and mineral
568 soil of a *Quercus petraea* forest sampled across seasons as visualized using Principle coordinate
569 analysis (PCoA) of the pairwise weighted UniFrac distances. Each point represents one composite
570 sample. Horizons: L – triangles, H – asterisks, Ah – circles, seasons: spring – green, summer –
571 yellow, autumn – brown, and winter – black.

572

573 Figure 3. Hierarchical clustering of the abundance of bacterial OTUs in the litter, organic and
574 mineral soil of a *Quercus petraea* forest across seasons. OTUs with a relative abundance > 0.5%
575 in > 4 samples are represented. Samples legend: L / H / A - litter / organic horizon / mineral
576 horizon, sp – spring, su – summer, au – autumn, wi – winter. The data represent the means of four
577 replicates per season.